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Evaluation of Pauline Five-Fold Operation Towards Missions Engagement Among Members of Anglican Diocese of Niger Delta North Port Harcourt Nigeria

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Abstract

Expositions on Pauline's Five-Fold Ministry, encompassing Apostles, Prophets, Evangelists, Pastors, and Teachers enumerated in Ephesians 4:11-13, as a foundational framework for equipping the Church for ministry has received multiple attention in research. However, evaluation of Pauline Five-Fold operation towards missions engagement among members of Anglican Diocese of Niger Delta North Port Harcourt Nigeria has not been explored adequately. This Paper evaluates its role in the effective missions engagement among members of the Anglican Diocese of Niger Delta North, Port Harcourt in the face of nominalism and docile nature of majority of the congregation. Using hermeneutic and qualitative descriptive approaches, hinged on the theoretical framework of Structural Functionalism. Findings reveal that integrating the Pauline Five-Fold Ministry will enhance the Diocese's capacity for effective missions work and strengthen its overall ecclesiastical structure, thereby fulfilling its missional objectives. Furthermore, deploying these ministry roles within the Diocese highlights how each office should contribute uniquely to the effectiveness and sustainability of missions efforts. Conclusively, the integration of the Five-Fold Ministry within the Diocese will foster a holistic and dynamic approach to getting everyone, both clergy and laity involved in ministry, thereby enhancing the missions programmes of the Diocese. It, therefore, recommended that the clerics and the laity should be adequately equipped through pastoralia and catechism on the work of ministry for the effective accomplishment of the mandate of missions in the Anglican Diocese of Niger Delta.

Keywords: Pauline Five-Fold Ministry, Evaluation, Missions, Anglican Diocese of Niger Delta North Port Harcourt, Effective Missionary Engagement

Introduction

Nominalism and lack of interest in any form of involvement in ministry is prevalent among members of the congregation of the Diocese of Niger Delta North Port Harcourt. This phenomenon which is exacerbated by the clergy /laity divide may be responsible for the lack leisure approach to missions engagement of the Diocese. While several Scholars have done so much research in the areas of development, implementation, and integration of missions work in the Anglican Communion in Nigeria, Pauline Five-Fold operation has not been evaluated towards mission engagement in the Anglican Diocese of Niger Delta North Port Harcourt, adequately assessed and documented for posterity. This is the gap this research seeks to fill.

While the Bible might not specifically use the word “mission,” the concept is rooted in biblical truth (Ruiter. et al 2004). The concept is profoundly embedded and recognized as a fundamental focus of the Church's mission. This idea is biblically validated and serves as a central element of the Church's purpose. The ministry of Jesus Christ culminated in establishing the primary thrust and expectation for the Church, which has given rise to and is classified as The Great Commission. The roadmap for this is clear when Jesus Christ told His disciples, “...and you shall be witnesses unto me both in Jerusalem, and in Judaea, and Samaria, and unto the uttermost part of the earth” (Acts1:8).

Missions as a term became a contemporary term only used freely, recently (Kollman 2011). Since the 1950s, there has been a notable increase in the usage of the term "mission" within Christian circles. This term has been employed to denote various concepts, including the dispatching of Missionaries, the endeavours undertaken by Missionaries, the specific regions where Missionaries operate, the Organizations facilitating Missions work, the broader non-Christian world or Mission field, and even the logistical hubs of Missionary operations. The initial adoption of this terminology to describe the dissemination of the gospel among populations is attributed to the Catholics, particularly Ignatius of Loyola and the Jesuits” (Bosch 2018).

Missions as a concept take its bearing from the ideology of Soteriology and it is the foundation of the Church. (Rozko 2014) If you remove this ingredient of the Church, it fails to meet expectations. Boach asserts that Missions and the gospel are intrinsically linked because missions is not just what the church does, but what it exists to accomplish. It is derived from the concept of *Missio Dei* in which God is saving a lost world. and so, the Trinity is sending; The Father sends the Son into the world to save it, and the Father and the Son send the Holy Spirit into the world and now the Holy Spirit is sending the Church (Bosch 2018). It is crucial, therefore, for the Church to comprehend the foundation upon which the Christian Mission stands. Only through this understanding can it persist in the missionary endeavour with fortitude and modesty, even in the face of misunderstanding and opposition from the world (2013).

Stott further asserts that the Church must not only grasp and comprehend its role in the pursuit of God's mission but actively employ all available resources to fulfill this significant task. The motivation and justification for this action are found in the Bible and so If we accept the Bible as the revelation of God's word, then the essential question becomes: How does Scripture reveal that "mission" is His intention for humanity? Boach in his postulation avers that traditionally, missions have been defined as a process involving the propagation of faith, the expansion of the sovereignty of God, and conversion. However, there have been various motives for missions that may not align with the ideology of *Missio Dei*. Motives that subjugate Indigenous peoples under colonial authorities; cultural motives, with the imposition of the missionary's culture as superior; romantic motives, fueled by the fantasy of traveling to distant and exotic lands and peoples; and ecclesiastical colonization, where one's own religious confession and church structure is exported to other territories. While some motives are clear in their objectives and align with desired expectations, such as theological motives emphasizing conversion, and personal commitment, eschatological motives focusing on the reign of God, and the motive of church planting emphasizing the formation of committed communities. An integral element of missions involves transcending cultural borders, often referred to as cross-cultural missions. This aspect of missions involves overcoming cultural barriers to engage with individuals who speak different languages, have distinct cultures, and require knowledge of salvation found solely in the Lord Jesus. It is a deliberate and

conscious effort to break loose barriers like tradition, culture, language, and norms placed by men (Olutunde 2015). The essential component in cross-cultural missions is reaching out to people whose language and culture are different and have not been converted. The importance of this aspect of missions is pivotal to the accomplishment of The Great Commission. Missionaries who therefore only reach out to people of their language and culture in a foreign land, cannot be classified as Cross-Cultural Missionaries. Nigerian Missionaries reaching out to Nigerians in Togo do not qualify to be classified as cross-cultural Missionaries or doing cross-cultural Missions, but they can be termed Transplanted Pastors (Nagassar 2016). He further avers that the motivation for Missions needs to be correct from the conceptual stage or else, the whole process will not meet the desired objective of accomplishing The Great Commission. The Unreached should be the objective of cross-cultural missions, not necessarily the spread of a denomination, or reaching out to diaspora members of a people in cross-cultural settings.

Apostle Paul fully understanding the enormity of the responsibility of the church regarding Missions, laid the structure for the church. In the book of Ephesians chapter 4, he outlined the structural foundation for the church in what has become known as the Five-Fold Ministry. Many writers have viewed this as a leadership structure or government. Others view it as the different areas of ministry or service in the church alongside others Paul listed in other passages in his different epistles. The fact remains that the Church was created to further the mission of God and as such, leadership and ministry must be seen in the light of the fulfillment of the mission of the church, and as such the Five-Fold ministry must serve as a precursor for effective deployment of the missions engagement of the church. The Five-Fold Ministry is founded on the message contained in Pauline's epistle to the church in Ephesians. This presupposes that the church is built around the five structural ministries to equip the church, (Believers) to be able to accomplish the task Christ has set for the church,

The Five-Fold Ministry is often referred to as the hand, because of the power of fingers working together. To buttress this fact, Paul, in several epistles, described the church as a body. (1 Corinthians 12:12,14, Romans 12:4-5, Ephesians 4:4.) The all-inclusiveness in the work of the ministry by all members was well captured in Ephesians 4 verse 7 "But unto every

one of us is given grace according to the measure of the gift of Christ. Paul laid much importance on the need to make all members of the church understand the importance of the concept of building the church on a solid structural foundation. It is therefore clear that the church is built on a structure of all-inclusiveness, hinged on the diversity of gifts of all members who are “called” to use their giftings in different areas to further the cause of God’s mission, passed unto the church by Jesus Christ (Bert 1983).

There has been a sharp departure from this Biblically structural setting well entrenched through several passages from the Bible. The early Church operated on a local level with Elders and Deacons as the offices of the Church whose positions were filled by men with special ministerial gifts defined in Ephesians 4:11. Guder & Darrell opined that “the theological reflection of the early church accompanied its mission and grappled with its challenges as a missionary church. The purpose of that theological labour was to equip and support the church in its missionary vocation” (Guder & Darrel 1998). The course of evolution of the church through the Apostolic era, to the post-Apostolic era, to the different stages of the Church evolution till date has occasioned a shift in the operation of the Five-Fold ministry as a structural base for most Churches (Shields 2011).

Study Design

This paper adopts a qualitative approach. The choice of this design is premised on the nature of the study which focuses on the role of the Five-Fold Ministry as a Precursor to the Effective Missions Engagement of the Anglican Diocese of Niger Delta North Port Harcourt. This will allow the Researcher to objectively balance personal observation, review data, to validate or refute information collected.

Conceptual Review

Brief History of The Anglican Diocese of Niger Delta North

The Diocese of Niger Delta North (DNDN) was inaugurated on May 16, 1996 (Ascension Day), at the Cathedral Church of Saint Paul Diobu, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. It is the 53rd Diocese in the Church of Nigeria (Anglican Communion) and the 4th to be created from the Diocese of Niger Delta, following Aba on January 9, 1972, Calabar on December 20, 1990, and Uyo on November 27, 1992. The Primate of the

Church of Nigeria, The Most Reverend Joseph Abiodun Adetiloye, presided over the inauguration service, which included the enthronement of The Right Reverend Samuel Onyuku Elenwo, who was translated from the residual Diocese of Niger Delta. He was succeeded by Right Reverend I.C.O Kattey on June 4th, 2000 a position he held until August 23rd, 2018 when Right Reverend Wisdom Budu Ihunwo was enthroned as the 3rd Bishop of the Diocese.

According to Onu, at the inauguration, the Diocese comprised the Cathedral Church of Saint Paul, Diobu; Archdeaconries of Port Harcourt, Ahoada, Ikwerre, Etche, Ogoni, Evo, Ikwerre South, and Eleme. Out of these initial Archdeaconries, the following have become Dioceses, Ogoni, Ahoada, Etche, Ikwerre, and Evo. The Diocese of Niger Delta North (DNDN) has grown over the years to now have one hundred and sixteen (116) Congregations comprising the Cathedral, nine (9) Deaneries, Twelve (12) Archdeaconries, and Chaplaincies, thirty-six other Parishes and fifty-eight (58) Station Churches (Onu 2022).

The Missions Work of the Diocese of Niger Delta North

The Diocese has continued to invest in foreign missions by sponsoring Clergy to different countries of the world This effort started in 2000 when two Churches then in the Diocese, St Andrew's Anglican Church Rumubiakani Port Harcourt, now in Evo Diocese, and St Matthew's Anglican Church Nkpogwu Port Harcourt, in Primatial Chaplaincy, responded to an invitation from the Bishop Jonathan Rumuliza of the Diocese of Cameroon in the Province of West Africa through the approval of Right Rev I.C.O Kattay to come and assist in the areas of Church planting because the entire Diocese had only five (5) Churches.

This gave rise to the sending of Missionaries to other foreign countries. Among the early foreign mission fields were: Cameroun, Ghana, Madagascar, South Sudan, Sierra Leone, and the Philippines. Presently, the Diocese of Niger Delta North has missionaries in 5 countries ministering in 9 churches: 1. Cote-Dvoire (CNMS) Mission, a. All Saints' Anglican Church, Abidjan, b. St. Philip's Anglican Church, San Pedro, c. New Covenant Church, Bouake. 2. Guinea and Guinea Bissau Mission, a. Ascension Anglican Church, Ratoma. 3. Italy Mission, a. Anglican Church of St. Anthony Abb, Padova, 4. Canada Mission, a. Anglican Church of Calvary, SaskaToon, SK, 5. Gabon Mission, a. Immanuel Anglican Church, Libreville, b. New Covenant Anglican Church, Port-

Gentil, c. Good Shepherd Church, Franceville. Mission to Gabon marked the planting of Anglicanism in that country (Onu 2024).

Biblical Basis for the Five-Fold Ministry (Ephesians 4:11-13)

The concept of the Five-Fold ministry is attributed to Apostle Paul as recorded in his letter to the Ephesian Church. “And he gave some apostles, and some, prophets, and some, evangelists; and some pastors, and teachers; For the perfecting of the saints, for the work of ministry, for the edifying of the body of Christ: Till we all come to the unity of the faith, and of the knowledge of the Son of God, unto a perfect man, unto the measure of the stature of the fulness of Christ. This passage lists five specific ministry roles that Jesus gave to the church: 1. Apostles - sent ones, pioneers who establish new works, 2. Prophets - those who speak God's words and reveal His heart, 3. Evangelists - those who proclaim the good news and win souls, 4. Pastors - shepherds who care for and guide the flock, 5. Teachers - those who instruct in the Word and doctrine. There are varying opinions about the Five-Fold ministry. Some writers view the gifts of apostles, prophets, evangelists, pastors, and teachers as offices, while others see these five gifts as functions of the individual. Some point to the overlap in the gifts and functions of the five-fold ministries, making it difficult to assign an office or function to a particular individual. (Wintoch.2003) Yet, others remain ambiguous regarding function or office and simply stress the leadership aspect of the five-fold gifts (Bayes 2010).

Textual Analysis of Ephesians 4:11-13

The process of understanding the concept of the Five-Fold Ministry will require first, a textual analysis of the text involved. The first important fact to note in the text is that the giver of the gift is Christ, “And He gave” This is indicative of the fact that Christ's role of equipping the Church for the task of fulfilling the mandate of making disciples of the nations as understood in the Great Commission. This fact is supported by verses 8 and 9 of Ephesians 4, talking about Christ's descension and ascension after accomplishing the task of freedom for humanity “He led captivity captive”. The need to prepare the Church can be seen as what gave rise to the gift.

The gift given has been specified and so focus is on the need for the gift. The first reason given for the need for the gifts is to equip the saints for

the work of ministry, and the second is for the edifying of the Church. It is unambiguous what the gifts are meant to accomplish. What may not be clear at this point is the reference to ministry, The Five-Fold gifts have been classified as ministries, so could this have been the ministries being referred to here? This question is quickly cleared by Apostle Paul in his letters to the Roman and Corinthian churches. In Romans 12: 6-8, he gave further clarification on the gifts and the ministries that ensue from them. In 1 Corinthians 12: 6-10, further insights are given to clarify what the different ministries are in the body of Christ. It is clear that the ministries in the church are beyond the five listed in Ephesians 4:11. This list of ministries is by no means exhaustive as we know that several ministries have evolved in the church over time, however, what has not changed is the fact that the Five-Fold gifts are saddled with the responsibility of preparing the church for ministry.

The next issue in our textual analysis is the idea of edification. The English word 'edify' comes from the Greek word "oikodomeo," which essentially means to build something. Translated, it means "to build a house" (Trenholm 2020). The Five-Fold ministry is to bring about the building of the Church. They are the builders of the structures upon which the Church rests. This is an important consideration as to what the Five-Fold ministry is supposed to do. The church is "built on the foundation of the apostles and prophets, with Christ Jesus Himself as the chief cornerstone." (Ephesians 2:20) Jesus Christ is most definitely active in the church today, His role as the cornerstone of the church was completed with His death, burial, resurrection, and ascension. The function of building the Church using all the ministries is an essential responsibility of the entire Five-Fold ministry working in unison to bring about a vibrant effective Church the understanding being that the Church is the new covenant people of God, rooted in the promises to Israel and inaugurated by the Holy Spirit, which refers both to all believers in Jesus Christ, both living and dead, and to local gatherings of believers (Morgan 2022).

The last part of our text reveals what is to be the result of the building process; disciples, who have become like Jesus Christ, fully embracing all that Christ stands for. The Church is designed by the concept of the Five-Fold ministry to be like a factory chumming out disciples not individually but by the collective effort of all the Five-Fold ministry Christ has made available to the Church. The process is a continuous one

until the Church becomes perfect. This fact of collectiveness is a theme that runs through some of Paul's letters to the Romans, Corinthians, and Ephesians. His use of comparing the Church to the body where no one can claim to be more important. The inability of the Church in contemporary times to effectively produce more disciples cannot be far from the inability of the Church to fully understand the purpose and use of the Five-Fold ministry.

Five-Fold Ministries as Office

Several writers and many denominations see the Five-Fold ministry from the point of view of Leadership offices with the apex office calling the shots. Wintoch opines that the emphasis is often on the significance of these offices in a local church, though important, often priority is placed on their interests, desire for power, and recognition, thereby excluding others often the "laity" from any involvement in church governance (2003). The Researcher agrees with the point of exclusion of others, especially the "laity" but does not understand the Five-Fold Ministry as a call to governance. It is the view of the Researcher from the textual study of the verses that conceptualize the Five-Fold Ministry that governance was not part of the intention of the Five-Fold Ministry though they play very vital roles in crafting leadership. It is this misconception that is promoting the neglect of using the gifts given to the Church to thrive in the core mandate of the Church which is The Great Commission. Leadership should be a product of the Five-Fold Ministry but they are to work to ensure that it thrives in equipping and edifying the Church.

Leadership in the Early Church

A copious study of Leadership in the early Church gives very clear direction on how leadership evolved. In Acts 6 verse 3, the first set of leaders apart from the Apostles were chosen and the qualifications for the office of Deacons were given; "men full of the Holy Spirit" This produced Stephen, Philip, Prochorus, Nicanor, Timor, Parmenas, and Nicolas a disciple from Antioch. These men were chosen for the work of ministry but the Leadership role was vested in the Apostles of Jesus. The Apostles gave direction but allowed people to express themselves in ministries. Stephen apart from sharing food in the church was also

involved in ministering the word that led to his martyrdom. Philip became the first established Evangelist.

The role of leadership was not always with the Apostles alone, there was the introduction of Elders. In the Jerusalem Council that took place to resolve the critical issue of circumcision in Acts 15, Peter an Apostle, and James an Elder, took charge and gave direction. The evolution of the leadership later introduced Bishops, in 1 Timothy 3:1-13, and Titus 1:5-9. Peter described himself as an Elder in the Church, not as an Apostle in 1 Peter 5: 1-5. Church leadership has evolved significantly, influenced by historical, cultural, and theological factors. Early models were often charismatic and familial, whereas modern leadership tends towards professionalization and autonomy. Today, the church continues to navigate challenges related to leadership discernment, authority, and balancing centralized with decentralized structures.

These three offices of Bishops, Deacons, and Elders are distinct, yet there is biblical precedent for overlap between the Five-Fold ministry and these. Scripture shows that it is possible to be a Deacon and hold a Five-Fold ministry, as evidenced by Philip, who is called both a Deacon and an Evangelist. Similarly, it is possible to be an Elder and hold a five-fold ministry, with Peter being referred to as both an Apostle and an Elder. However, there are no reference that suggests that all Elders must be Five-Fold leaders. The qualification for Eldership is character, not a Five-Fold ministry gift. Conversely, Five-Fold ministers are not required to be Elders in a local church (Hilder 2023).

Five-Fold Ministries as a Function

The other divide in the discussion on the Five-Fold Ministry sees it from the point of view of function. The argument in favour of this line of thought is derived from the purposes which have been given in the Textual analysis as; 1. to equip the saints for the work of ministry, 2. to build up the body of Christ to produce disciples, 3. Perpetual, until we all attain the unity of the faith. There is a need to answer the question; do individuals with any of the Five-Fold gifts receive titles such as apostle, or prophet because they occasionally perform certain functions, or because they hold clearly defined positions within their communities? Clarifying this issue will help the church more effectively fulfill God's plan. An office is the Body of Christ's public recognition that an individual possesses a certain gift and is authorized to minister that gift

in an official capacity (Bayes 2010). These five gifts are seen as functions of the individual, not the office. This is so because an individual can occupy an office yet cannot function in that capacity. A person can be ordained as a Pastor yet does not fulfill the functions of a Pastor even when he/she is addressed by that designation. The function is based on the gift not necessarily the office

The understanding of the functions of the Five-Fold Ministries will impact in great measure the missions work of the Church. This is because all ministries to which every member of the Church has a gift with varying levels of grace according to Ephesians 4:7, Romans 12:3, and 1 Corinthians 12:7, implies a large workforce for the Great Commission in different capacities. The gift of The Five-Fold Ministries is to produce capacities in the work of making known the reign of the Kingdom of God. Every single believer is to be involved in using his or her own gifts to build God's kingdom. All ministries in the Church are to not only help in building the Church but to enlarge it. The idea is that each member of the church body has a role to play in furthering God's kingdom (Kovalevich 2022).

The leaders alone cannot do all the work that needs to be done of taking the gospel to the unreached or those not yet converted. This responsibility is for every believer or member of the Church. The disparity between "clergy" and "laity" breeds Nominal Christianity. This refers to people who identify as Christians in name only, without genuine personal faith in Christ or commitment to biblical principles. Nominal Christians are individuals who may attend church or identify with a Christian denomination, but their faith doesn't significantly influence their daily lives or decisions. They are Christians in name only, as Christ's teachings and presence do not play a central role in their lives. This is indicative of the fact that people are not involved in ministries because there is no discipleship. The absence of disciples means very little if any is done to impact the core mandate of the Great Commission, missions. Straube succinctly explains that all believers are called to serve the Lord through prayer, worship, and giving; to serve the church community through encouragement, comfort, and love; and to serve the world by sharing the message of Jesus Christ's saving grace. This provides plenty of responsibility without the need to take on additional leadership roles (Straube 2016).

Understanding the Five-Fold Ministry Roles

- a. Apostle:** The word ‘apostle’ is defined as “one chosen and sent with a message”. Originally associated with the Disciples of Jesus Christ but became seen as pioneers or visionaries within the Christian faith sent out by the church, with the responsibility of establishing new churches, spreading the Gospel, and providing foundational leadership. In the early church. Apostles have a burden to ground their church in solid biblical teaching, as exemplified in Acts 11 when Paul and Barnabas spent two years in Antioch, teaching and equipping the believers there. Apostles are driven by a desire to train and raise church leaders who will reach full maturity, eventually releasing them to take on leadership roles. Apostles continue to break new ground, often engaging in missionary work to unreached or list reached People groups where the gospel has not found root.
- b. Prophet:** Prophets serve as God’s mouthpieces, delivering divine messages and guidance to the Church. Their role involves foretelling future events, providing correction, giving direction, and encouraging believers. Prophets reveal God’s heart to His people, offering guidance to individuals and the church body, and giving revelation, often including interpretation, application, and timing. Examples can be found in the book of Acts 13, such as Barnabas, and Simeon also known as Niger, Philip’s daughters, and Agabus in Acts 21. Prophetic voices continue to inspire and direct the Church toward God’s will.
- c. Evangelist:** Evangelists are passionate about sharing the Gospel with those not yet converted. They possess a unique ability to communicate the message of Christ effectively, leading people to faith and salvation. Biblical evangelists like Philip the Evangelist (Acts 21:8) traveled extensively to spread the good news. Their foremost desire is to see people come into the kingdom, leaving the discipleship process to others. They teach others how to win people to Christ. Growth and bring growth to the local church and the kingdom of God. They work more on outreach although as a result of nominalism, they now engage in in-reach.
- d. Pastors:** Pastors, or shepherds, provide spiritual care and oversight to the local congregation. They are responsible for nurturing and guiding believers, offering counseling, and ensuring

the well-being of their flock. The pastoral role is akin to that of a shepherd tending to sheep, emphasizing protection, provision, and direction. Today, pastors play a central role in church life, often serving as the primary spiritual caregivers. The office of the pastor is the most recognized of the Five-Fold Ministry roles. Due to a lack of understanding of the other four roles, and the fusion of the leadership role of the local assembly with the pastoral functions, those with the gift to function in the other roles have often had to become pastors.

- e. Teachers:** Teachers have the gift of explaining and interpreting the scriptures, making them accessible and understandable. They play a critical role in discipleship, helping believers grow in their knowledge and application of God's Word. Teachers bring out the revelation of the hidden things in the Word. Biblical teachers like Paul dedicated much of their ministry to educating early Christians. Contemporary teachers continue this tradition, often leading Bible studies, writing theological works, and teaching in various educational settings.

The Five-Fold ministry is meant to train, equip, and empower all believers for ministry so that the church grows in unity, maturity, and Christlikeness. The Apostles, Prophets, Evangelists, Pastors, and Teachers are to work together to build up the body of Christ as their roles overlap as well as individuals can operate at one time or the other in more than one capacity.

1. The thumb is the Apostle as he can function in all five gifts. as a pioneer.
2. The index finger is the Prophet as God uses him to point the way
3. The long finger is the Evangelist due to his long reach.
4. The ring finger is the Pastor because he is joined to the sheep in marriage.
5. The little finger is the Teacher because he brings balance to the body of Christ

Source: <https://www.ffministry.com/blog/.what-is-the-five-fold-ministry/>

Collaborative Synergy Between the Five-Fold Ministry

Each of these roles are essential for the growth, unity, maturity of the Church, and involvement in God's missional assignment, especially if there is collaborative synergy between them, and this can lead to a more effective and holistic ministry. The shared vision and common goal of building and equipping the Church ensures that each role supports the others and works towards the same objectives, fostering harmony and effectiveness in ministry efforts. Since each role brings unique strengths and perspectives, this allows for a more comprehensive approach to building the Church. Mutual respect and support among the different roles, recognizing and valuing the unique contributions of each role fosters a collaborative environment where everyone feels appreciated and empowered to fulfill their calling. A church that effectively integrates all five roles can address the spiritual, emotional, and practical needs of

its members more comprehensively leading to both numerical and spiritual growth, and a tendency to become missional as each role complements the others creating a sense of community and shared purpose. By working together, these leaders equip the saints for ministry, build up the body of Christ, and strive towards unity and maturity in the faith and fulfillment of the Great Commission.

Operation of the Five-Fold Ministry in The Anglican Diocese of Niger Delta North Port Harcourt

The Anglican Diocese of Niger Delta North Port Harcourt which is a part of the global Anglican Communion, has its unique approaches to incorporating the Apostolic, Prophetic, Evangelistic Pastoral, and Teaching Ministries, (APEPT) within its context. The Anglican Communion is episcopal-led and Synodically governed (Orioye 2024). It operates within a hierarchical structure with the bishop at the head at the Diocesan level, and. Synods and Boards provide governance. Bishops, clergy, and lay representatives collaborate to make decisions that affect the entire church.

The Anglican Diocese of Niger Delta North Port Harcourt recognizes the operation of the APEPT but appropriates it to the Clergy, where the bishops and the Pastors are acknowledged as the operators of the Five-Fold ministries almost at the exclusion of the laity. This is evident in the fact that APEPT is perceived as synonymous with leadership roles not necessarily as gifts to fulfill functions. It can be argued that the clergy is taken from the laity but the fact is that operating in any of the Five-Fold Ministries does not require first becoming a Pastor.

Bishops are seen as Apostolic Figures married to the Diocese by the symbolic wearing of the ring during their consecration. (Church of Nigeria Anglican Communion.) They are responsible for planting new churches, providing oversight, and establishing doctrinal foundations. The bishop is the only one recognized as an Apostle as he is consecrated to the pontifical lineage of the Apostolic order of Peter. This is without prejudice to the fact that he is still recognized as a Pastor. At ordination, the Pastor is given the role of a Priest, Pastor, Evangelist, and, Teacher with the expectation that with the help of the Holy Spirit, he will be able to minister to the physical and spiritual needs of the congregation.

The drawbacks of this conceptualization are multiple. The first is the fact that granted that there can be overlap in functions, given time, the

responsibility could become overbearing on the individual dealing with a congregation, and also considering that he is also expected to do administrative duties of running the local parish. Secondly, APEPT, are gifts in individuals to be used for equipping the Church not necessarily in the leader whose biblical qualification is good character. Thirdly, the laity are left out of ministry and are expected to assist the Pastor instead of doing their ministry with their gifts. This has led to the laity not getting involved in ministry. Lay Readers are licensed to assist Pastors during worship service and Pastors in waiting who were called catechists are given the designation of Teachers or Evangelist until they undergo Theological training to become Pastors.

Structural Functionalism Theory

Structural Functionalism is a sociological theory that views society as a complex system with various parts working together to promote stability and social order that serves a purpose, and each is indispensable for the continued existence of others and society as a whole (Encyclopedia Britannica 2024) Each part of society has a function that contributes to the continued equilibrium of the whole. This theoretical framework can be applied to understand the impact of the Five-Fold Ministry on the missions work of the Anglican Diocese of Niger Delta North, Port Harcourt.

Relevance of this Theory to this Study

The application of Structural Functionalism to the Five-Fold Ministry of the Anglican Diocese of Niger Delta North can be understood from four perspectives:

1. Understanding the Roles

Apostles: Function as pioneers and visionaries, establishing new churches and providing direction. Their role contributes to the growth and expansion of the church. **Prophets:** Offer guidance and correction through divine insights, ensuring the church remains aligned with its spiritual mission. **Missionaries** fit into this role of the Apostles. **Evangelists:** Focus on outreach and bringing new members into the church, vital for the church's growth and sustainability. **Pastors:** Provide care and counseling, maintaining the well-being of the congregation, which is crucial for the church's internal stability. **Teachers:** Educate and

instruct the congregation, ensuring doctrinal soundness and continuity of faith.

2. Functions of the Five-Fold Ministry in the Church's Mission

Each role within the Five-Fold Ministry integrates to maintain the stability of the church. For example, while Evangelists bring in new members, Pastors and teachers ensure these members are nurtured and grounded in the faith. Apostles and Prophets can help the church adapt to new challenges and societal changes, ensuring that the church remains relevant and responsive. The Church's mission is achieved through the collaborative efforts of the Five-Fold Ministry, each contributing to the overall goal of spreading the Gospel and serving the community. Beyond their explicit roles, each ministry contributes to the implicit functions, such as creating a sense of community, providing social support, and fostering moral development.

3. Interdependence of various roles. The synergy among the Five-Fold Ministry enhances the church's ability to fulfill its mission effectively. For example:

- Prophetic insights can guide the strategic decisions of apostles.
- Evangelists' outreach efforts are supported by the nurturing environment created by pastors and teachers.

4. Maintaining Social Order and Community Resilience

- The Five-Fold Ministry helps maintain social order within the church community by upholding shared values and norms.
- By addressing both spiritual and social needs, the ministry contributes to community resilience, helping the church navigate.

Structural Functionalism provides a useful framework for analyzing the impact of the Five-Fold Ministry on the missions work of the Anglican Diocese of Niger Delta North, Port Harcourt. By viewing the ministry roles as interdependent parts of a larger system, this theory helps explain how each role contributes to the church's mission's stability, growth, and effectiveness. The approach highlights the importance of each role's function and the synergy created by their interaction, ultimately supporting the church's goal of spreading the Gospel and serving the community.

Conclusion

This paper has attempted to examine the Five-Fold Ministry as a foundation upon which the missions work of the Anglican Diocese of Niger Delta North Port Harcourt can be anchored for more effective and sustainable growth. Findings show that the clergy in the Anglican Diocese of Niger Delta North Port Harcourt are picked and sent on foreign missions as missionary without any training in cross cultural missions and without any support beyond payment of their salaries by individuals or assigned churches. The sole dependence on clergy for missions work itself poses a problem as the laity are not given any opportunity to participate in the missions work of the Diocese beyond quarterly offering raised for the missions work.

This paper shows that there is the need to first build a solid ministry base in the church using the Five-Fold Ministries as a catalyst to equip people in different areas of ministries which ultimately helps in achieving the Great commission. It therefore becomes a collective effort of collaboration of all members, clergy and laity, all using their gifts to bring about the accomplishment of God's mission as given in the Great Commission. This Paper shows also that it is an error to assume that because one is ordained as a clergy, he is endowed with the Five-Fold ministry gifts as practiced by the Diocese. The need therefore to separate office and function becomes paramount. Helping people discover their areas of gift becomes important for effectiveness and sustainability of the missions work of the Diocese and this can only be possible if the Five-Fold ministry is allowed to thrive becoming a precursor to effective deployment for missions.

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